

SCL Test Science Projects for EOSC Future (WP6.3):

COVID-19 metadata findability and interoperability in EOSC (META-COVID)

Interview guide for a qualitative study to characterise the contextual metadata and workflows in selected research infrastructures

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The study planned is part of the Horizon 2020 funded project EOSC Future (<https://eoscfuture.eu/>). In Work Package 6, Task 6.3 of EOSC Future, Test Science Projects (TSP) are specified. This document refers to the TSP “COVID-19 metadata findability and interoperability in EOSC” (short: META-COVID). The objective of this TSP is to develop a framework for a metadata model characterising the contextual metadata and especially the research approach followed in the domain represented by each research infrastructure (RI). Contextual metadata refers to data about the research process that generated the data, and / or objects that describe that activity and to data about the ‘inputs’ into the research process – grants, people, organisations, regulators, research infrastructures etc. In the TSP a specific focus should be given to the modelling of the artifact “research activity”. The intention is to apply an iterative process of consensus building amongst experts drawn from different disciplines in the life sciences and social sciences and humanities.

As a first step semi-structured interviews with representatives of the participating RIs will be performed by ECRIN. The procedure consists of two steps:

- a) Preparatory video conference
- b) Semi-structured interview with selected representatives from the RIs

All RIs participating in the TSP will have an interview. From the life sciences, the following infrastructures will be included:

- ECRIN
- BBMRI
- EATRIS
- EU-Openscreen
- EMBL

From social sciences and humanities the following infrastructures will be included:

- CESSDA (represented by the Finnish Social Science Data Archive, FSD)
- CLARIN

1. Preparatory video conference

As preparation for this video conference, a short document will be distributed to our contact persons of the individual RIs. This document summarises the objectives of the TSP, the work plan, the results achieved so far and the plan for the interviews. In addition, the list of questions to be asked in the main interview will be distributed beforehand. Before the preparatory interview, ECRIN will check [the results of the survey on metadata standards used by the RIs](#) for relevance to the interviews. In the preparatory video conference, which will be scheduled for 30 to 60 minutes, the following points will be clarified:

- a) The objectives of the study
- b) Clarification of interview questions, definitions and terminology (e.g., contextual metadata, research graph)
- c) Identification of documents in the RI related to the study objectives. These documents will be collected by ECRIN and analysed.
- d) Nomination of 1-2 experts from the RI for the semi-structured interview, covering the areas and expertise needed for the interview.

The preparatory video conference will be recorded to support notes taking. The recording will be destroyed once the study is complete, and the final report has been written. After the preparatory video conference, the commitment of the nominated experts will be sought and a date for the semi-structured interview agreed (via Doodle). The time interval between the preparatory video conference and the semi-structured interview should not be longer than 4 weeks.

2. Semi-structured interview

In the study, the technique of semi-structured interviews will be applied. In-depth and semi-structured interviews explore the experiences of participants and the meanings they attribute to them. Researchers encourage participants to talk about issues pertinent to the research question by asking open-ended questions, usually in one-to-one interviews. The interviewer might re-word, re-order or clarify the questions to further investigate topics introduced by the respondent (taken from: <https://academic.oup.com/intqhc/article/19/6/349/1791966?login=false>).

The details of the study are specified in a study protocol. The semi-structured interviews will be conducted by three experts from ECRIN (M. Panagiotopoulou, S. Canham, C. Ohmann). It is planned to record the video conferences. The recording will be destroyed once the study is complete, and the final report has been written. The duration of the semi-structured interview will be around 60 minutes. The interview guide will be piloted first with ECRIN and then with BMMRI. It may be that after the piloting the interview questions have to be adapted but this should be limited as much as possible. In case information from the piloted RIs is missing due to adapted questions, these RIs will be contacted via email. Notes from the semi-structured interviews will be made and returned to participants for comments. The information revealed in the interview will be documented in a structured answer sheet. A first version will be created before starting the interviews and adapted after the pilot interviews, if necessary. After the interview, a content analysis will be performed, systematically organising data into structured formats and the information will be coded with existing ontologies and metadata schemas.

The semi-structured interview will consist of a mix of structured and unstructured interview. Some questions are predetermined, others may come up during the interview, thus allowing for some flexibility. The interview will be structured into two parts:

- 1) Objective aspects of the use of contextual metadata in the RI's domain
- 2) Opinion-based and subjective views of the interviewees about use and potential value of contextual metadata in their scientific domain

Prepared questions:

1. Objective aspects of the use of contextual metadata in the RI's domain

At the start of the semi-standardised interview, it will be established whether the information provided to ECRIN beforehand has been understood and that the documents provided make sense.

1.1 What does 'contextual metadata' mean to your RI?

In the interview with the RI, we should find out

- a) How is the RI organising its services and tasks (contextual metadata linked to the work of the RI directly)?
- b) How the research activities are structured. How are the RIs dealing with contextual metadata of the research activities managed in or by the RIs?

Based on the analysis of the services and the research activities, a first attempt can be made to characterise the contextual metadata in and behind the RI. For questions 1.1 and 1.2 it is important to differentiate between contextual metadata that are directly applied within and by the RI and contextual metadata that are of relevance for the domain represented by the RI.

The interview should provide a preliminary list of elements of contextual metadata. This list will later be reconciled with existing metadata schemas and ontologies.

If the structure of contextual metadata has been clarified adequately, the next step is to ask for metadata schemas used by the RI or linked to the research activities that are covered by the RI's scope.

1.2 What elements of contextual metadata of the resources/digital objects are modelled in the metadata schemas applied at your research RI (research organisations, researchers, services, projects, funders, etc.)?

Starting from the list that has been developed under question 1.1, it will be checked, whether the identified contextual metadata elements are covered by the metadata schemas in use by the RI. Here it should be ascertained whether the contextual metadata element is already applied by the RI or whether it is foreseen but not yet implemented.

Part of the discussion will be to find out whether there are gaps in the use of contextual metadata. If this is the case, options should be discussed to improve the situation.

If the use of contextual metadata in or by the RI has been sufficiently discussed and documented, the next question will be related to the possibilities to harvest these metadata from outside.

1.3 What services, protocols, standards, APIs are implemented in your RI to support harvesting of contextual metadata from outside (e.g., public or non-public API)?

The objective of the TSP is to develop a framework for a metadata model, characterising the research approach and workflow across infrastructures. The discussion of question 1.3 will be a first step to find out which contextual metadata elements can be assessed and therefore used as input into the development of such a framework.

Currently, there is a trend to link contextual metadata to so-called research graphs. A **research process graph** refers to a graph-based approach for modelling research processes. A research graph is a **graph database** that interlinks information from various resources related to the research process by using nodes (also called points or vertices) which are connected by edges (links, lines). Examples of research graphs are the OpenAIRE, interlinking funders, organisations, researchers, research communities and publishers and the PID graph, establishing connections between different entities within the research

landscape. In the next question, it should be discussed whether the RI is already working with research process graphs or is planning to do so.

1.4 Are the contextual metadata used in your RI already linked to a research process graph or is it planned to do so?

To be able to discuss these questions, the experts from the RIs should have an overview of the existing research graphs. Here, it is important to identify the type of research process graph already in use or planned to be used and the extent to which the (planned) implementation is already covering the contextual metadata elements identified in question 1.2.

2. Opinion-based and subjective views of the interviewees about use and potential value of contextual metadata in their scientific domain

The following question is dealing with the potential value of contextual metadata.

2.1 Do you believe that a greater generation and use of contextual metadata would be valuable enough to justify the additional effort that would likely be involved?

- If yes, can you describe the specific contextual data points and possible relations that would be of most value, if available and / or used more widely, and why?
- If no, can you explain in detail why not?

Do you think that your views are representative of the major stakeholders in your research field?

The next question deals with aspects of contextual metadata cross domains and disciplines. It is important for the development of a framework for a metadata model across RI's.

2.2 From your viewpoint, how could interoperability for contextual metadata between RIs be improved?

Here we want to elucidate statements and comments from the RI, how to better relate contextual metadata between RIs. This is a rather open question with free-flowing discussion.

Do you think that your views are representative of the major stakeholders in your research field?

2.3 What could be the best organisational framework for moving this work forward within EOSC?

The last question deals with the link of the work of the TSP with the EOSC. In the TSP, integrating EOSC core service or onboarding resources to EOSC is not foreseen. Registration of the framework in the EOSC catalogue is certainly an option. Nevertheless, the interview should explore and discuss options to better integrate the work into the EOSC. Prerequisite of the discussion is a basic knowledge of the structure and work around the EOSC.

Do you think that your views are representative of the major stakeholders in your research field?